

Density, viscosity and speed of sound based acoustical properties of halogenated symmetric double Schiff bases of 1,1'-bis(4-aminophenyl)cyclohexane in 1,4-dioxane at 308.15 K

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Abstract : The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) (2 MHz) of 1,4-dioxane solutions of halogenated symmetric double Schiff bases were measured at 308.15 K. Various acoustical parameters such as specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{CI}$), and viscous relaxation time (τ) were determined using ρ , η and U data. The results were interpreted in terms of molecular interactions occurring in the solutions. Linear increase of U , Z , R_m , b , $(\alpha/f^2)_{CI}$, τ and V_f and linear decrease of κ_s , L_f and π with increasing concentration of Schiff bases supported existence of strong molecular interactions in the solution and solvophilic nature of the Schiff bases. The nature, size and position of halogen substituent also affected acoustical properties and hence molecular interactions.

Keywords : Speed of sound, density, viscosity, halogenated symmetric double Schiff bases, molecular interactions and solvation number.

Introduction

Schiff bases or imines or azomethines are condensation products of aromatic primary amines with aromatic aldehydes or ketones, which have played a vital role in the progress of chemical sciences¹. Schiff bases are well-known for their impressive applications such as the preparation of dyes, liquid crystals, and powerful corrosion inhibitors². Schiff bases possess biological importance as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory and antiparasitic³⁻⁵. They are also useful as starting materials for the synthesis of drugs like antibiotics, antidepressant, antiallergic, antiphlogistic and antitumor^{6,7}.

Recent developments have found use of ultrasonic energy in engineering, agriculture and medicine. The drug-solvent molecular interactions play vital role in understanding drug action⁸. Viscometric properties provide valuable clues for solute-solvent interactions in the solution phase. Such results can be helpful in predicting the absorption of drugs and transport of drugs across the biological membranes⁹. Therefore, it may be interesting to investigate variation of their properties with concen-

tration for understanding the mechanism of drug action. Ultrasonic is a non-destructive technique for study of pharmaco-kinetics, drug action, organic liquids, binary solutions and epoxy resin solutions^{10,11}. Speed of sound and viscosity data help in understanding drug action through various kinds of physicochemical interactions e.g. ionic or covalent, charge-transfer, hydrogen bonding, ionic-dipole interaction, hydrophilic interaction¹². By measuring density, viscosity, and speed of sound of solution various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters can be determined^{13,14}. These parameters provide un-
tween physical properties, which help in physicochemical investigations and these investigation play an important role in understanding the nature and patterns of drug action¹⁵.

In continuation with speed of sound and related study on hydroxyl and nitro substituted symmetric double Schiff bases^{13,16,17} (Scheme 1), here with we have reported measurements of speed of sound, density and viscosity of five halogenated symmetric double Schiff bases in 1,4-dioxane at 308.15 K. The main aim of the present work was

to examine the nature, size and position of halogen substituent on density, viscosity and speed of sound and related acoustical parameters to understand the molecular interactions in the Schiff bases solutions.

Experimental

1,4-Dioxane used in the present study was supplied by Allied Chemical Corporation, Vadodara, and purified according to literature method¹⁸. Schiff bases DSB-1 to DSB-5 were synthesized and crystallized according to our previous work¹⁹. The stock Schiff bases solutions (0.10 mol dm⁻³) were prepared at 308.15 K and from them a series of solutions were prepared. The solutions were stored in air tight flasks.

Measurements :

The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) measurements on 1,4-dioxane and DSB-1 to DSB-5 solutions were measured at 308.15 K by using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi) Model No. F-81, operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to ± 0.1 kg m⁻³, 0.01 mPa s and $\pm 0.15\%$, respectively.

Results and discussion

The ρ , η and U data of 1,4-dioxane, DSB-1 to DSB-5 at 308.15 K are reported in Table 1. Using ρ , η and U data of Schiff bases solutions, various acoustical parameters such as specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), free

volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient $(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}$ and viscous relaxation time (τ) were determined according to our previous work^{13,17} and are reported in Table 2. These parameters were correlated with concentration (C) of Schiff bases and a good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration (C) of Schiff bases was observed.

From Table 1, it is evident that ρ ($\gamma = 0.981$ to 0.999), η ($\gamma = 0.962$ – 0.993) and U ($\gamma = 0.986$ – 0.996) increased with increasing concentration of Schiff bases confirming existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions²⁰. The position of chlorine substituent (DSB-1, DSB-2 and DSB-3) did not show marginal change in the magnitudes of ρ and η values with increasing concentration of DSB-1 to DSB-3 but considerable change in U is observed (DSB-2 > DSB-1 > DSB-3). The nature of halogen substituents (-F, -Cl and -Br) and their positions caused change in ρ , η and U respectively in the order : DSB-4 > DSB-3 > DSB-5; DSB-3 > DSB-4 > DSB-5 and DSB-4 > DSB-3 > DSB-5, respectively. Thus, nature, size and position of halogen substituents affected density, viscosity, speed of sound and determined acoustical parameters of the Schiff bases solutions.

From Table 3, it is observed that Z ($\gamma = 0.959$ to 0.994), R_m ($\gamma = 0.999$ to 1.000), b ($\gamma = 0.999$ to 1.000), τ ($\gamma = 0.952$ to 0.990), $(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}$ ($\gamma = 0.931$ to 0.988) and V_f ($\gamma = 0.924$ to 0.983) increased linearly, while κ_s ($\gamma = -0.983$ to -0.993), L_f ($\gamma = -0.980$ to -0.994) and π ($\gamma = -0.991$ to -0.998) decreased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases confirmed presence of strong molecular

DSB-1 : R = 2-Cl; DSB-2 : R = 3-Cl; DSB-3 : R = 4-Cl; DSB-4 : R = 3-Br and DSB-5 : R = 4-F

Scheme 1

Table 1. Density, viscosity and speed of sound of DSB-1 to DSB-5 in 1,4-dioxane at 308.15 K

Parameter	Concentration (mol dm ⁻³)						
	0	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.1
	DSB-1						
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1039	1050	1055	1059	1062	1065	1068
$\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa s)	1.042	1.111	1.175	1.214	1.260	1.303	1.350
U (m s ⁻¹)	1319.6	1329.4	1339.2	1345.6	1351.0	1357.4	1365.2
	DSB-2						
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1039	1050	1055	1059	1062	1065	1068
$\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa s)	1.042	1.110	1.179	1.211	1.280	1.308	1.364
U (m s ⁻¹)	1319.6	1337.2	1343.6	1349.4	1356.6	1363.8	1369.2
	DSB-3						
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1039	1047	1049	1057	1060	1065	1068
$\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa s)	1.042	1.129	1.160	1.250	1.297	1.339	1.370
U (m s ⁻¹)	1319.6	1327.0	1333.6	1340.6	1348.8	1361.2	1364.4
	DSB-4						
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1039	1049	1053	1058	1.062	1066	1070
$\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa s)	1.042	1.086	1.147	1.216	1.276	1.345	1.376
U (m s ⁻¹)	1319.6	1341.2	1348.4	1356.0	1363.4	1369.0	1373.2
	DSB-5						
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1039	1043	1045	1048	1052	1055	1058
$\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa s)	1.042	1.048	1.137	1.168	1.201	1.243	1.290
U (m s ⁻¹)	1319.6	1323.2	1331.8	1338.4	1345.4	1350.8	1357.2

Table 2. Acoustical parameters of DSB-1 to DSB-5 in 1,4-dioxane at 308.15 K

Conc. (mol dm ⁻³)	$Z \times 10^{-6}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	$R_m \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{1/3} mol ⁻¹)	$b \times 10^5$ (m ³)	$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)
0.0	1.371	5.527	9.299	8.355	4.92	5.111		7.682	
	DSB-1								
0.01	1.396	5.389	9.440	8.462	4.86	5.162	1.159	8.009	1.188
0.02	1.413	5.285	9.631	8.615	4.81	5.143	1.229	8.223	1.211
0.04	1.425	5.215	10.034	8.963	4.78	4.995	1.240	8.465	1.241
0.06	1.435	5.159	10.440	9.316	4.76	4.844	1.260	8.668	1.265
0.08	1.446	5.096	10.845	9.664	4.73	4.705	1.278	8.863	1.288
0.10	1.458	5.024	11.251	10.009	4.69	4.567	1.303	9.009	1.301
	DSB-2								
0.01	1.404	5.326	9.459	8.461	4.83	5.306	1.218	7.884	1.136
0.02	1.417	5.251	9.642	8.613	4.80	5.330	1.237	8.252	1.211
0.04	1.428	5.191	10.054	8.970	4.77	5.135	1.240	8.378	1.225
0.06	1.441	5.117	10.455	9.314	4.74	5.032	1.256	8.732	1.269
0.08	1.452	5.048	10.862	9.663	4.70	4.855	1.282	8.802	1.272
0.10	1.462	4.995	11.262	10.008	4.68	4.745	1.286	9.085	1.308
	DSB-3								
0.01	1.393	5.424	9.462	8.486	4.88	5.275	1.132	8.165	1.213
0.02	1.401	5.360	9.675	8.664	4.85	5.201	1.143	8.289	1.226
0.04	1.407	5.264	10.042	8.980	4.80	5.147	1.198	8.773	1.290
0.06	1.411	5.186	10.457	9.334	4.77	4.991	1.204	8.969	1.311

Table-2 (contd.)

0.08	1.415	5.068	10.855	9.664	4.71	4.839	1.234	9.048	1.315
0.10	1.417	5.030	11.249	10.010	4.70	4.687	1.266	9.187	1.328
DSB-4									
0.01	1.407	5.300	9.568	8.553	4.82	5.013	1.307	7.673	1.128
0.02	1.420	5.223	9.854	8.795	4.79	4.966	1.310	7.99	1.169
0.04	1.435	5.140	10.430	9.295	4.75	4.771	1.324	8.336	1.212
0.06	1.448	5.066	11.009	9.797	4.71	4.577	1.351	8.619	1.247
0.08	1.459	5.005	11.576	10.291	4.68	4.421	1.360	8.974	1.293
0.10	1.469	4.956	12.132	10.778	4.66	4.225	1.421	9.095	1.306
DSB-5									
0.01	1.380	5.476	9.460	8.491	4.90	5.177	1.266	7.651	1.140
0.02	1.392	5.395	9.650	8.644	4.86	5.259	1.282	8.177	1.211
0.04	1.403	5.327	10.011	8.955	4.83	5.097	1.288	8.292	1.222
0.06	1.415	5.251	10.359	9.253	4.80	4.954	1.314	8.407	1.232
0.08	1.425	5.195	10.71	9.556	4.77	4.839	1.323	8.607	1.257
0.10	1.436	5.131	11.061	9.856	4.74	4.739	1.325	8.825	1.282

Table 3. The least square equations and correlation coefficients for DSB-1 to DSB-5 in 1,4-dioxane at 308.15 K

Parameter	Least square equations (Correlation coefficients, γ)				
	DSB-1	DSB-2	DSB-3	DSB-4	DSB-5
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	186.03C+1050.2 (0.981)	187.95C+1050 (0.985)	238.9C+1045.3 (0.988)	225.75C+1048 (0.994)	167.4C+1041.5 (0.999)
η (mPa s)	2.426C+1.1088 (0.991)	2.335C+1.1283 (0.993)	2.7216C+1.1167 (0.982)	2.935C+1.0959 (0.993)	2.3471C+1.0599 (0.966)
U (m s ⁻¹)	362.36C+1329.2 (0.986)	348C+1335.3 (0.996)	425.86C+1323.9 (0.992)	348.27C+1340.5 (0.986)	355.18C+1322.8 (0.988)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.6348C+1.396 (0.985)	0.6214C+1.4019 (0.993)	0.2493C+1.3945 (0.979)	0.6696C+1.4051 (0.990)	0.5959C+1.3777 (0.994)
$\kappa_a \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-3.7047C+5.3861 (-0.983)	-3.5616C+5.3387 (-0.993)	-4.4745C+5.4532 (-0.993)	-3.72C+5.3072 (-0.987)	-3.6507C+5.4845 (-0.991)
$R_m \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{1/3} mol ⁻¹)	20.169C+9.2314 (1)	20.13C+9.2489 (0.999)	19.828C+9.2656 (0.999)	28.645C+9.2646 (0.999)	17.728C+9.293 (0.999)
$b \times 10^5$ (m ³)	17.302C+8.2776 (0.999)	17.291C+8.2781 (0.999)	16.883C+8.3174 (0.999)	24.794C+8.3038 (1)	15.163C+8.3424 (1)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-1.6795C+4.8584 (-0.980)	-1.6493C+4.8385 (-0.994)	-2.063C+4.8916 (-0.988)	-1.7836C+4.8272 (-0.989)	-1.6712C+4.903 (-0.990)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-6.8763C+5.2577 (-0.998)	-7.25C+5.4544 (-0.995)	-6.4608C+5.3571 (-0.991)	-8.9066C+5.1223 (-0.998)	-6.49C+5.367 (-0.995)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	1.317C+1.1768 (0.924)	0.8597C+1.2084 (0.958)	1.4545C+1.121 (0.983)	1.1647C+1.2853 (0.950)	0.6745C+1.2648 (0.965)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	10.837C+7.9796 (0.990)	10.45C+8.0288 (0.984)	11.522C+8.1432 (0.957)	25.766C+7.4577 (0.952)	8.055C+7.9783 (0.988)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	1.2477C+1.1845 (0.988)	1.6211C+1.1531 (0.934)	1.3077C+1.2129 (0.931)	1.9712C+1.124 (0.985)	1.2723C+1.1583 (0.916)

interactions in the solutions. The decrease of κ_s and L_f with increasing C , further confirmed aggregation of solvent molecules around solute molecules resulting in decrease of intermolecular distance²¹⁻²⁴. The decrease of π with increasing concentration of Schiff bases suggested decrease of cohesive forces, which resulted in increase of free volume. The increase in free volume indicated loosening of close packing of the molecules due to strong molecular interactions. Thus, free volume is inverse function of internal pressure and hence increase in internal pressure led to decrease in free volume²⁵.

Both $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ and τ depend upon ρ , η and U at constant temperature. Increase of $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ and τ with C can be explained in terms of motion of intermolecular forces. A contribution of acoustical relaxation is accounted due to entropy fluctuation associated in solution of thermodynamically formed physical entity. The competing solute-solute interaction disrupt the structure formed as a result of solvent-solute interaction and consequently entropy fluctuation increases with increasing solute-solute interaction.

The solvation number (S_n) can be expressed as :

$$S_n = \frac{M_2}{M_1 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_s}{\kappa_{s1}}\right) \left(\frac{100-X}{X}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of solvent and solute, respectively. The solvation number is a measure of structure forming or structure breaking tendency of the solute in a solution. Fig. 1 shows the plots of S_n against concentration of Schiff bases. S_n increased nonlinearly with increasing concentration of Schiff bases indicating competing solvent-solute and solute-solute interactions^{17,26}. The effect of nature, size and positions of halogen substituents also affected the solvation phenomenon (Fig. 1). The position, size and nature of halogen substituents caused different solvation tendency ($DSB-5 > DSB-3 > DSB-4 > DSB-1$). Thus, various acoustical parameters suggested the presence of strong molecular interactions and further supported by positive values of solvation number.

The lone pairs of electrons of azomethine and 1,4-dioxane and halogen groups are electronegative groups, while hydrogen of azomethine is an electropositive group. The dipole-dipole interaction of opposite type leads to

Fig. 1. The plots of S_n against C at 308.15 K in 1,4-dioxane.

structure formation, while of the same type lead to breaking of the structure formed previously. The azomethine hydrogen of DSB-1 can form intramolecular $-N=CH---Cl$ bonding and intermolecular hydrogen bonding with 1,4-dioxane. DSB-2 to DSB-5 can form intermolecular

$-CH=N---X$ ($X=Cl, Br$ or F) bonding. At lower concentration solvent-solute interaction is predominant over solute-solute interaction, while at higher concentration solute-solute interaction is predominant over solvent-solute interaction and consequently led to breaking of the structure formed as a result of dispersive forces. Thus, both solvent-solute and solute-solute interactions are observed in the Schiff base solutions. The size and position of halogen substituent also affected molecular interactions.

Conclusions

Various acoustical parameters and solvation number revealed solvophilic nature of Schiff bases. Above mentioned parameters suggested existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. The size, nature and position of the halogen groups also affected acoustical properties of the Schiff bases solutions.

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